

WHITE PAPER #2

SODALITE

Software Defined AppLication Infrastructures management
and Engineering

Extremely optimizing software applications on Cloud and HPC solutions

We are currently living in a software defined world. Cloud and HPC systems are the backends of practically everything we use on a daily basis. Without them, there are no weather reports/predictions, maps, mail, messaging, TV, radio, music, etc. No smart assistants either. In this field, SODALITE is bringing new solutions to deal easier and faster with big amounts of data and to comply with security and privacy issues.

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38%

Within IoT challenges the most recurrent is found in complexity of technical problems

SODALITE provides application for developers and infrastructure operators with tools that abstract their application and infrastructure requirements to enable simpler and faster development, deployment, operation, and execution of heterogeneous applications.

SODALITE can be applied in several and complex environments such heterogeneous, software defined, high-performance, cloud infrastructures, with a particular focus on performance, quality, manageability, and reliability.

A serie of RESOURCES are provided under SODALITE toolset, as follows:

- pattern-based abstraction library, including application, infrastructure and an absolute novum, performance abstractions
- design and programming model for full-stack application and infrastructure descriptions, using abstraction library
- deployment framework, enabling static optimisation of the so-abstracted applications onto specific infrastructures
- automated run-time optimisation and management of so-deployed applications.

Empowering European Industry

This toolset will directly support Digital Transformation of European Industry through

- increasing design and runtime effectiveness of software-defined infrastructures, to ensure high performance execution over dynamic heterogeneous execution environments which translated to other words, will speed up the performance while keeping the focus on quality and consumption aspects;
- increasing simplicity of modelling applications and infrastructures, to improve manageability, collaboration, and time to market. Thus, improved models will be better understood and used by other experts in the value chain such consultants, sales teams, technology providers/vendors.

SODALITE provides application developers and infrastructure operators with tools that abstract their application and infrastructure requirements to enable simpler and faster development, deployment, operation, and execution of heterogeneous applications reflecting diverse circumstances over heterogeneous, software- defined, high-performance, cloud infrastructures, with a particular focus on performance, quality, manageability, and reliability.

Ensure high-performance execution over dynamic heterogeneous execution environments; increasing simplicity of modelling applications and infrastructures, to improve manageability, collaboration, and time to market.

The full stack of SODALITE is divided into five different layers which have in common four pillars, in these pillars the heterogeneity, security and privacy, service quality and semantic intelligence remain the essential ones to deploy applications in a different way and comply with the strategic aspects that keep accurate this toolset for a fast go to market.

Whereas, the layers developed in SODALITE rely on the aforementioned pillars for a well execution assuring the heterogeneous requirements are taken into account as well as, security/privacy/policy terms are conformed with the European regulations and applicable standards. In addition, the stack implements semantic modelling for the database, with the end to offer an appealing and complete system for developers who are specialized in complex systems, managing big amounts of complex data.

The Full Stack

Smart IDE supports semantic reasoning and context-aware content assistance (IntelliSense), this is an intelligent searching and validation service when designing resources and application models. The W3C standards are valuable in this process due to enriching and validating our TOSCA-compliant Knowledge Graphs.

PESTO uses IaC (Infrastructure as a Code) and TOSCA with the orchestrator for building heterogeneous runtime images, applying xOpera lightweight orchestrator to Kubernetes and Edge computing.

FindIaC Bug aims at finding and fixing syntactical-structural and semantic errors in IaC artifacts prior to deploying and executing them. Moreover, aims at unifying the approach to predict various smells in IaC using semantic web technologies and model-driven architecture.

REFIT, the spotlight put on monitoring and reconfiguration is the component that dynamically allocates resources to the multiple containerized applications running on nodes and manages the workflow capabilities for HPC (High Performance Computing) applications.

POET is focused on the optimization across the performance so it gives an unified modelling for HPC/Cloud infrastructures with diverse hardware and automates performance optimisation while improving application scaling by using performance models.

Real Scenarios

Snow Water is a scenario where the main concern is to avoid water scarcity in determined areas, regions or mountain ranges. This case is highly related to climate change effects, the world is evolving towards hottest temperatures and water is one of the victims. Hence, SODALITE is offering an alternative solution to control and prevent these events. In this context, mountain images can be a solution to predict water availability in concrete zones, peaks of mountains where the majority of water is stored in snow packs.

Furthermore, most of these images are in public webs. SODALITE simplifies the design, deployment and maintenance of online pipelines of heterogeneous components, alleviating the complexity of manually scaling complex IT applications. Real time monitoring operations helps detect bottlenecks and devise optimal options for reconfiguration and redeployment.

More scalability = more data processing power = more accurate and abundant snow and water availability data

In silico spinal trials for bone operations assessment and decision-support system for spinal operations consisting of a data store component, capable of providing efficient data access from heterogeneous compute resources and simulation process chain facilitating comprehensive data analytics for in-silico clinical trials.

The problem that occurs in this type of operation is in the simulation pipeline, which is composed out of several components, implemented in different programming languages and based on different execution paradigms. The integration of this simulation process chain and the inclusion of additional steps is an extremely tedious work and requires a platform expert once it comes to a change in the infrastructure the pipeline is deployed on.

By the possibility to more easily deploy and use complex simulation pipelines on cloud computing infrastructures in combination with HPC the effort for applying simulation methodologies, this combination of the two technologies will provide every pipeline component with the needed resources and features like data protection out of the box.

Whereas, the patients will benefit from an improved device design and personalized medicine in implant application and development which is expected to reduce device failure rates and by that to improve the quality of life after implantation surgery.

Automotive is one of the biggest industries worldwide and with emerging trends, such as autonomous vehicles, connected cars or ride sharing, is becoming increasingly data driven. This means that enormous amounts of data must be collected, curated, aggregated, analysed, monitored and controlled, both in the Cloud, and increasingly, in the vehicle itself at the network Edge.

Furthermore, there is the growing expectation of drivers to have on-demand services, adapted to their personal preferences, that flow seamlessly between countries and service providers while respecting their individual rights to privacy and security. From the industry perspective, there is a growing demand to be able to provision such services quickly, reliably and efficiently across multiple countries, infrastructure and legal environments.

A key challenge, however, remains in separating between essential vehicle and safety-critical services that must be run directly in the vehicle regardless of connectivity state (e.g. vehicle diagnostics, collision avoidance, pathfinding, driver drowsiness detection and alerting, etc.), infotainment services delivered from the Cloud to the vehicle's head unit (e.g. streaming media), and fully Cloud-based applications and dashboards that utilize vehicular data (e.g. fleet trackers).

The work in SODALITE has enabled the use case to employ an additional level of abstraction, providing for infrastructure-level adaptation and deployment refactoring. As the EC has clearly identified in its Data Strategy, Digital Strategy, Industrial Strategy and recovery plan, Cloud computing is a key objective to increase Europe's sovereignty. Within the context of vehicle services, the integration of vehicular and personal data are a key challenge in the next generation of personalized vehicle services.

ATOS

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XLAB

XLAB is a Slovenian R&D performing SME, with a strong commercial background (see below) and the corresponding research group. XLAB Research is recognized as one of the strongest computer science research teams outside the academic world in Slovenia. It employs 40 people including 8 with a PhD and the vast majority with MSc or BSc degrees. XLAB as a whole employs 65 people and closely collaborates with 43 external experts, providing the whole company with access to more than 100 experts in the fields of computer science, electronics and mathematics as well as design and marketing.

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